

TEACHING METHODS OF "UZBEK FOLK MUSIC CREATIVITY" SUBJECT IN THE FIELD OF MUSIC EDUCATION

A.E. Rakhimova

Independent Researcher at Urgench State Pedagogical Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15312262>

Abstract. *The given article presents substantiated information about the methods of teaching "Uzbek Folk Music Creativity" subject in the field of music education, including teaching techniques and mechanisms for their practical application.*

Keywords: *folk, music, creativity, national tradition, customs, heritage, values, ceremony, genre, artistry, style, method, technique, performance, practice.*

Introduction.

It is important to suggest that students in the field of music education should pay great attention to the use of game-based teaching methods when studying the subject "Uzbek Folk Music Creativity," by incorporating various repertoires and customs from different areas of Uzbek folk music. Therefore, it is necessary for students to master the method of game-based learning in preparation for their future professional activities. This method, based on the integration of applied ethnopedagogy, art, and physical culture, helps students successfully engage with national traditions, as it reflects a leading form of activity characteristic of student life [1].

The second stage of this method focuses on a deeper study of musical folklore as an integral component. An important feature of this approach is the recognition not only of group work but also of individual forms of creative artistic activity.

Overall, the proposed project and new form of musical-pedagogical activity have proven themselves over time. It offers the unique experience of a folklore-ethnographic amateur association that aims to revive traditional forms of Uzbek folk musical creativity and highlights the similarities between folklore and educational practices. The system for familiarizing students with traditional artistic heritage is based on a variety of activities integrated around family singing as a priority that centers around kinship relationships. Ensemble performance in joint programs serves as a means for students to understand musical folklore through integration into family traditions and collective participation.

Definitely, the folk performance skills acquired by all participants during joint expeditions to different regions form the foundation of vocal mastery. Through exposure to folk culture within the family, students can gain artistic experience and develop creatively while preserving and understanding the deep roots and canons of tradition in the process of assimilating musical folklore materials [5].

Methodology.

Folk folklore presents a unified form for organizing the creative, educational, and instructional activities of youth and students of different ages working together as a collective. As noted by CIS scholar S.G. Zagradskaya, such experience originates from the authentic family traditions of rural populations. However, this does not exclude the possibility of distinguishing

students and adolescents into an independent group, which may require a separate pedagogical approach [3].

Certainly, in the learning process of mastering this subject, students are encouraged to participate in festivals and ceremonial ensembles created based on materials from Uzbek folk musical creativity. This represents a truly local phenomenon that organically integrates folk culture into the social life of the higher education institution. The oral method of engaging with tradition is recognized as a leading pedagogical approach for developing a sense of folkloric intonation.

What is more important, students assimilation of Uzbek folk musical creativity relies on their intuitive imitation of the folk musical speech of the instructor. This process helps root traditional practices into the students' educational experience.

Within the curriculum of higher education institutions, the pedagogical concept of teaching musical folklore retains its unique features. This is reflected not only in the outcomes but also in the entire process of immersing into the world of folk culture—through games, rituals, and movement.

Efforts to identify the most effective forms and methods of instruction within higher education continue. The issue of scientifically grounded and adequately in-depth study of traditional folklore heritage is becoming increasingly urgent. Modern educational practice stands at the beginning of a path that seeks to preserve and develop the rich cultural and pedagogical legacy that remains relevant to this day.

Besides that, incorporating the content of cultural traditions into various academic disciplines helps provide a comprehensive understanding of the history of Uzbek folk musical creativity and allows for a multifaceted interpretation of the dominant meanings of ethnic culture [5].

The growing need to reassess the role of Uzbek folk musical creativity in the professional, pedagogical, and methodological preparation of music education students is gaining attention in scholarly research. Among local scholars, Q. Panjiyev emphasizes in his studies:

“In globalized world of today, we must study the traditions of Uzbek folk musical creativity more thoroughly and ensure that they become the foundation of future music teachers’ professional activities. It is precisely through this path that we can instill national spirituality and mentality in our students, as well as develop their professional, pedagogical, and methodological capacities.

Admittedly, we have yet to seriously address this issue. Instead, we currently rely heavily on foreign music repertoires. This is somewhat regrettable. Nevertheless, to make Uzbek folk musical creativity the cornerstone of future music teachers’ professional, methodological, and pedagogical training, we must carry out extensive scientific research.” [1]

Indeed, the real state of pedagogical practice shows that the process of teaching Uzbek folk musical creativity requires a specifically designed combination of in-class and extracurricular activities in primary and middle school settings within general secondary education. The limited structure of music lessons in schools, which only allows students to acquire the minimal necessary knowledge for performing Uzbek folk and traditional music, has been recognized by teachers as neglecting the great potential of informal interaction with students outside the classroom.

Within the bachelor’s degree curriculum in music education, it is essential that mandatory subjects and student-selected courses prioritize learning about national culture and history. Students come to understand that the structure of classroom activities, the principles of lesson design, and content requirements often differ significantly from the natural forms of traditional

Uzbek folk music practices.

It is worth mentioning that there are more opportunities than ever to introduce students to cultural traditions. The purposeful and systematic nature of educational courses ensures the consistent and dynamic development of the key categories, concepts, ideas, norms, and standards that reflect the behavior accepted in traditional society. On one side, this process is linked with classroom lessons, and on the other, it is associated with various forms of extracurricular activity. Together, they represent a shift from theoretical learning to the direct, hands-on assimilation of folk traditions [2].

Within the framework of this subject, students come to understand that ethnocultural education is recognized as an essential factor in fostering spiritual development, intergenerational continuity, and connection with national sources of life. Folklore is increasingly important in fulfilling the moral and professional education tasks and in developing the creative abilities of the younger generation [3]. Gradually, the teaching of musical folklore is being integrated into the experimental curricula of educational institutions.

The development of the curriculum for the subject Uzbek Folk Musical Creativity is aimed at promoting in-depth study of music in general secondary education based on folklore. The educational process is instructional, developmental, and systematic, and it takes into account the specific features and nature of the applied folklore tools—such as oral transmission, variability, the balance between collective and individual participation. All educational activities are based on the stylistic approach of folk art.

Certainly, the teaching of the subject Uzbek Folk Musical Creativity is closely interconnected with the cycle of disciplines in higher education. Interdisciplinary links with subjects such as native language, literature, natural sciences, regional studies, national history, and others are clearly observed. One of the main elements of the music curriculum is the development of Uzbek vocal performance within musical folklore materials, which is built on examples of musical and poetic folk creativity. This highlights the importance of special exercises aimed at vocal development, speech improvement, and enhancement of singing culture.

In studying the stylistics of musical folklore, students base their learning on the subject of Uzbek Folk Musical Creativity as a dynamic method of developing musical culture. The traditional method of learning folk songs through improvisation opens up vast opportunities for revealing students' creative abilities and artistic thinking [4]. Studying musical folklore involves not only acquiring a set of expressive artistic tools or the ability to perform a certain number of folk songs, but also understanding the mutual interaction of these tools as part of an inseparable artistic system.

The methodology of teaching students' creative music based on folk musical materials is built as an educational system. As the student's vocal apparatus develops, the natural open vocal tone gradually forms based on speech-related sound messages. The unique vocal style of Uzbek folk songs emerges through the combination of speech-like intonation, articulation, and the free use of vocal registers [5].

Teaching the subject Uzbek Folk Musical Creativity in higher education is highly relevant in the context of Uzbekistan. However, in light of today's globalized world, there is a pressing need to improve it by developing modern methodologies for lesson content, creating teaching aids, expanding musical and folklore materials, and providing methodological recommendations to enhance students' creative activity.

Throughout the 20th century, various forms and methods of teaching traditional culture

were recognized as essential components of artistic education for students, with Uzbek Folk Musical Creativity forming the foundation. In the field of pedagogy within music education, higher education institutions need to employ new pedagogical technologies and implement innovative types of learning in both educational and training processes, this is a crucial stage in modern teaching practice.

The growing interest of future music educators in musical folklore today reflects the diverse interests of modern students. It underscores the need to seek out such forms of music education that introduce students to national culture as an integral part of their spiritual potential. In such circumstances, structured instruction in the study of folklore heritage becomes an essential educational tool.

During the years of independence, a new, tested form of folklore education emerged students began to work within a structured system based on the curriculum of the subject Uzbek Folk Musical Creativity both during class and extracurricular activities, with a focus on ethnographic profiling. The aim of music specialization is to revive and preserve folklore traditions that are organically woven into the socio-pedagogical environment of the population. In our view, the potential of forming an internal creative system of ethnomusical pedagogical culture holds vast educational and developmental value, the importance of which is difficult to overstate in today's educational environment.

Folk music creativity schools can take many forms: ethnically experienced, artistically oriented, or creatively focused [4].

At the bachelor's level of music education, the increasing number of students being trained in pedagogy necessitates the implementation of broad educational practices in teaching the subject Uzbek Folk Musical Creativity, using various forms of educational organization. This includes incorporating the study of Uzbek folklore into folk and traditional music culture schools, existing art schools, and general secondary schools. Today's students are tomorrow's music teachers—thus, equipping them with national music traditions and teaching them based on Uzbek folk musical creativity requires improving the pedagogical conditions, mechanisms, and tools necessary for ensuring professional, pedagogical, and methodological preparation.

Students must develop and justify unique forms and methods of teaching Uzbek folk musical creativity and culture that are adapted to various conditions. They should also recognize the leading role that cultural and educational institutions must play in maintaining the continuity of musical folklore. Reaching a high level of professional understanding in studying and mastering traditional heritage, education, and instruction is essential [2].

The national-local component formed through elements of ethnoculture is widely applied in both secondary and higher educational institutions. Courses related to the teaching of musical folklore in connection with Uzbek Folk Musical Creativity continue to be introduced in both public and private higher education institutions specializing in music education and pedagogy.

As musical and pedagogical practice expands, a new direction in education has emerged: the methodological activation of specialization in the field of Uzbek Folk Musical Creativity within music education. This includes the development of various teaching aids, textbooks, recommendations, authorial programs, lesson plans, and specialized courses. It also encourages the growth of pedagogical activity related to the teaching of musical folklore. The methodology for using national intonation in traditional music calls for the development of pedagogical practices related to the intonational features found in examples of folk musical creativity. These features are

reflected in the works performed by representatives of traditional solo performance schools.

Results and discussion. Improving modern technologies and the use of electronic tools and teaching methods is having a positive impact on today's educational landscape, including the teaching of Uzbek Folk Musical Creativity. Web technology specialists are developing the innovative content of a unified educational environment. However, this process also highlights the need for qualified personnel in the music education system. There is a lack of educational resources, specialized learning platforms, and expert support. Most importantly, due to limitations in research and practical bases, there is a growing need to further develop progressive practices in the field of pedagogical musical folklore activities.

Improving the professional work of future music teachers requires several essential tools and initiatives. These include: an electronic library; computer software for folklore pedagogical practice; a comprehensive database on traditional and contemporary folklore genres; organizing some student educational and pedagogical internships in the form of musical folklore expeditions (fieldwork); lecture courses; repositories for coursework and theses; visual teaching aids, and more.

Implementing such an educational project seems to us both important and promising. It can be realized through the collective efforts of research groups [5].

Thus, by examining the art studies, musicology, folklore studies, and cultural perspectives of Uzbek folk musical creativity as well as its evolutionary processes and the historical practice of teaching musical folklore as a conceptual approach to pedagogical activity in this field has been successfully identified. The creative re-examination of musical folklore involves ensuring the continuity of knowledge about folklore and studying it as a field of science, a national style, and artistic skill. This integration has harmoniously united the authentic and contemporary elements of Uzbek folk musical creativity.

The modern practice and theory of teaching musical folklore is gradually transforming into a logically structured system through a consistent sequence of practical and scientific-research experiences. It has evolved from specific didactics into a more goal-oriented form of education, creating a unified understanding of teaching methodologies. It can be concluded that:

- In improving the professional and methodological preparation of students in the field of music education, a new form of education is undoubtedly emerging. This involves methodical and pedagogical organization of teaching the subject Uzbek Folk Musical Creativity using time-tested methods of learning and teaching traditional music across various performance directions—research, popularization, teaching, and methodology.
- Updating the forms of organizing the educational process—such as various modified versions of folklore ensembles and studios—has opened up new prospects for the development of musical folklore education in accordance with the curricula of higher education institutions.
- Introducing various forms of vocal performance with different performance types (mixed, uniform, solo) and age compositions into music education helps students absorb the unique characteristics of folk music related to Uzbek folk musical creativity. This substantiates a qualitatively different content for methodological and pedagogical guidance.
- A research-based approach to teaching Uzbek folk musical creativity, as a functionally enhanced type of music pedagogy, fosters the development of special heuristic

methodological techniques and artistic tools. These serve to restore and immerse learners in the environment of folk creativity, where the method of engaging with traditional culture becomes a stable creative mode for preserving musical heritage.

- The teaching of Uzbek Folk Musical Creativity is based on the oral expression of students in the music education field, who professionally understand the specific features of folklore performance. Through this, entry into and adaptation to folk traditions is grounded in shared methods and experiences.

The assimilation of the musical, cultural, and historical heritage gathered through musical folklore-ethnographic expeditions organized across local regions has been recognized as one of the most essential tools in music education. It functions both as a method of pedagogical observation and as a research technique based on elements of folklore art.

Local ethnographic material serves as a distinctive feature of musical-folklore education by embodying and transmitting traditional folk culture in artistic form.

The improvement of concert-performance formats for showcasing folklore art—such as ethnographic concerts, research-based presentations, lectures, exhibitions, and audience-engaged performances has shaped the promotional direction of musical-pedagogical activities in the field of folklore performance.

Developing modern methods for enhancing the teaching of Uzbek folk musical creativity defines a qualitatively new stage in educational practice.

Moreover, the use of interdisciplinary scientific knowledge, new technologies, and communication tools is improving the teaching of musical folklore.

Thus, within the general structure of the educational space, the use of various forms and methods of Uzbek folk musical creativity has been characterized by the effectiveness of pedagogical engagement with cultural heritage. Its success depends on the step-by-step improvement of teaching Uzbek folk music traditions. However, an analysis of current practices under conditions of globalization has revealed that:

- The system of teaching Uzbek folk musical creativity within the undergraduate music education curriculum is still not sufficiently regulated;
- There remain inconsistencies in pedagogical approaches within the methodology of teaching ethno-cultural creativity.

There are no unified principles and conceptual approaches in the content of educational activities for teaching traditional cultural heritage. All of this once again confirms the necessity of addressing the issue of improving professional and methodological training in the field of "Uzbek Folk Music Creation" through the teaching process in the direction of music education.

In teaching the subject of Uzbek folk music creation, it is recognized as one of the effective methods of learning the subject to organize musical folklore expeditions by students across our country's regions, recording the songs and tunes available among the population, compiling their records, collecting information about the author and performer of the work, and transcribing it.

In this process, the fieldwork of musical-folklore expeditions conducted by students, the processing and reworking of the collected materials, and the reporting of results are of great importance. Students should prepare written data, audio-video recordings, complete listings, electronic records, text notebooks, and expedition journals (including film numbering, tracks, records, song names, genres, number of voices, recording locations, birth year, and full names of performers).

Decoding methodology. Decoding is the ability to linearly hear one or several pitch-related sounds and timbre sounds, and a method of defining its scale. It involves distinguishing their unique features in Uzbek oral professional musicology by contrasting the canons. It also includes transcribing low-quality recordings, identifying technical and intonation defects in performance, and recognizing differences in altered pitch levels, shortened and expanded intervals, and singing in an unnatural order. The metrorhythmic importance of the musical and poetic texts lies in their interrelationship between the versification of musical speech and intonational turns.

Method for working with literary and musical texts. It involves enhancing the focus on intonational transcription, performance methods, interlingual songs, and dialect. It also involves checking decoding by singing sounds, accepting characteristic intonations, methods of folk music performance, principles of melodic development, and methods of change. It also includes identifying the characteristics of polyphony, the presentation fabric, and the nature and dramaturgy of the folklore sample.

In such a case, adherence to the distinctive features of folk music, the use of variation and improvisation from folk methods in musical folklore transcription, mastering the literacy of correcting musical material, arranging Uzbek folk songs, transferring the arrangement to various performance compositions, decoding musical material through polyphonic composition, and identifying the characteristics of instrumental accompaniment in the genres of folklore are carried out.

Folk Performance Methods. The characteristics of local musical styles and performance techniques, as well as the combination of musical and speech elements in the performance of Uzbek folk music vocalists, require students to strictly adhere to professional performance traditions. The selection of repertoire is of significant importance in both instrumental and vocal performances. In some higher education institutions, it has become a common practice to include works in the repertoire that are unrelated to Uzbek folk music creation. In our opinion, this approach is entirely incorrect. In this process, the distinctive features of folk music, such as breathing, articulation, the dialectical-speech message of sound, vocal dynamics, the tonality structure of the work, melodic construction, rhythm, tempo, elements of sound volume, ensemble structure, musical instruments' harmony, timbre ensemble, and the unified style of voice production, all require attention to various national characteristics.

Conclusion. The significance of the opportunities for teaching the subject of Uzbek folk music creation is evident in the numerous performance methods it includes, such as working with female and male voices, utilizing range capabilities, the individuality of timbre, choral singing, ensemble singing feelings, and the technical aspects of solo and ensemble performance. By applying these methods, students were able to learn the scope and depth of the teaching methodologies for Uzbek folk music creation and understand how to utilize them.

By summarising it should be suggested the methods of using traditional Uzbek instruments. The general characteristics of traditional Uzbek instrumental performance culture, the classification of Uzbek folk instruments, the analysis of the practical meaning of the music in solo and accompanying [practical] instrumental performance, the practice of instrumental performance, the history of the instruments, the conditions of their distribution, the age-related synchronization of male and female musical cultures in instrumental music, and the organic connection between music, song, dance, speech, and dramaturgy in the musical folklore culture were all integrated into the learning process.

REFERENCES

1. Panjiyev K.B. Improving the Professional Training of Future Music Teachers through Uzbek Folk Songs. Monograph. 2022, p. 202.
2. Ibrohimov O.A. "Uzbek Folk Music Creation" (Methodological Recommendations, Part 1), Tashkent. 1994. P. 62.
3. Karabaev U. Ethnoculture (Traditional Folk Culture): Textbook. Tashkent, Sharq. 2005. P. 240.
4. Panjiev, K. (2022). Theoretical principles of improving professional training of future music teachers through uzbek folk songs. *Development and innovations in science*, 1(3), 4-9.
5. Panjiev Qurboniyoz Berdiyevich. Uzbek Family Ceremony Music and Its Description of Genre Candidate of Arts, Associate Professor of Tashkent State, Pedagogical University Named After Nizami, Tashkent, Uzbekistan. *International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (IJTSRD) Volume 6 Issue 1, November-December 2021* Available Online: www.ijtsrd.com e-ISSN: 2456 – 6470